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**Multi-actor Network to Boost Short Food Supply Chains
Across Europe**

**Welcome to the latest edition of the
EU4Advice Newsletter!**

EU4Advice at the Cross Living Lab event!

presented by **Maarten Klop**, gathered experts and stakeholders to collaborate on innovative urban and food solutions. The event fostered dynamic discussions, knowledge sharing, and creative approaches to addressing challenges in urban food systems, emphasizing sustainability and community-driven practices.

[Learn more](#)

The Living Labs Series

During the Cross Living Lab event, we had the opportunity to interview the **leaders of the Living Labs** to learn how they began working in local food systems and the motivations behind their involvement. **Watch the interviews!**

Living Lab The Netherlands

Mark Frederiks shared his extensive experience developing short food supply chains.

Over the past 15 years, Frederiks has been instrumental in creating numerous local food systems, focusing on community-supported agriculture and direct market access for farmers.

[Learn more](#)

Living Lab Spain

Jorge Molero, from Fundación Entretantos, and the Living Lab Spain manager shared insights from his work with local food systems.

He emphasized the benefits of regional approaches to food production, which support farmers, promote healthier food, and strengthen communities.

[Learn More](#)

VIKTORIA NAGY

Living Lab Hungary

Viktoria Nagy, manager of the Living Lab Hungary, spoke about her commitment to local food and small-scale production.

She highlighted the role of local food associations in supporting short food supply chains.

[Learn More](#)

DAVIE PHILIP

Living Lab Ireland

Davie Philip, manager of Living Lab Ireland, shared his journey into local food systems.

He emphasized how living labs enhance short food supply chains and foster resilient local economies.

[Learn More](#)

Network News

The COREnet Experience at the Cross Living Labs Amsterdam

Eva Jennings

Research Office in the Rural Economy
& Development Programme (REDP)

Jan Willem van der Schans

Co-Founder Task Force Korte Keten
(Task Force Short Supply Chain)

During the Cross Living Lab event, we welcomed members from our sister project CORENET.

Eva Jennings and **Jan Willem van der Schans**, representatives of COREnet, attended the EU4Advice Cross Living Lab event in the Netherlands.

The COREnet project addresses the fragmented landscape of knowledge in food systems and the lack of clarity surrounding essential skills and competencies across all phases, from farm to fork. The project focuses on supporting the systematic development of more effective Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs) advising. By bringing together public, private, and civic advisors, CoreNET fosters IT-enabled peer-to-peer learning and mutual support to strengthen collaboration and improve SFSC practices across Europe.

[Learn more](#)

Collaboration is key

During the summer, EU4Advice had the privilege of participating in a collaborative meeting with several

the Sustainable Food System
Innovation Platform.

[Learn more](#)

More News & Events

EU4Advice at
the Reformaten
Event

EU4Advice will
join the Synergy
Days 2024

New
communication
& dissemination
partner

[Events](#)

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